

TRANSFORMATION WITH GRIEF IN *NORWEGIAN WOOD* AND *NEVER LET ME GO*

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Abstract

This study aims to explore a comprehensive analysis of how grief functions as a catalyst for personal transformation in these two notable literary works, Haruki Murakami's *Norwegian Wood* (1987) and Kazuo Ishiguro's *Never Let Me Go* (2005), and what insights can be drawn from their narratives. These two novels are about the lives of some young people growing and understanding life and coming to terms with the obstacles of living. This study analyzes the two novels using the framework of Sigmund Freud's mourning and melancholia. The characters of both stories deal with a sense of loss, either of loved ones or of an ideal life. The theory of mourning and melancholia has been applied in the study to analyze the characters' procession of grief at their loss. Along with Freud's theory, Judith Butler's explanation of mourning has also been used to discuss the two novels. Through a comparative analysis, the study explores how grief shapes the central characters and influences their journeys toward self-discovery and growth.

Keywords: Mourning; Melancholia; Memory; Trauma; Acceptance.

INTRODUCTION

Psychoanalysis of literary texts has helped explain and understand the psyche and behaviors of the characters of a story. Psychoanalysis gives us an insight into the character's mental state and an overview of their thoughts and feelings that influence their actions. Sigmund Freud's interpretation has been one of the popular ones to be relied on for psychoanalysis. Freud's theory of mourning and melancholia can be used to examine the characters' actions that insinuate depression or apathy toward life.

The mourning process is the attachment transition from one object to a different one because the last object has been lost. When the mourner fails to complete mourning and remains stuck in the grief of the loss, melancholia attaches itself to the individual. Melancholia is a state of deep depression and despair, causing a departure from the usual attitude towards life, and the cause of melancholia is often unknown to the sufferer. This research explores the role of mourning and melancholia in *Never Let Me Go* and *Norwegian Wood*. The characters of both novels suffer from a sense of loss. In *Never Let Me Go*, the significant characters are clones created to serve humans till the clones die.

The loss for the clones was the loss of everyday life. However, no hidden fixation on the lost ideology pushed them into melancholia because they created a life with each other within their boundaries, which positively impacted their mourning process. In *Norwegian Wood*, the characters clearly showed the symptoms of melancholia. Naoko's mourning process over the loss of her lover, Kizuki, was incomplete. As Kizuki was an intimate part of Naoko's teenage life, his sudden death made her life stuck in those times when she was with him, making her believe she deserved to be with him in the end.

Objectives:

1. To examine the impact of grief and transformation with grief in Haruki Murakami's *Norwegian Wood* and *Never Let Me Go*.
2. To explore coping mechanisms and transformation processes in Haruki Murakami's *Norwegian Wood* and *Never Let Me Go*.

LITERATURE REVIEW

This paper is a psychoanalysis of the novels *Norwegian Wood* and *Never Let Me Go*, mainly using the theories of Sigmund Freud and Judith Butler. This literature review consists of several articles containing studies conducted on particular novels and psychoanalysis.

The most significant sources of theories for this research have been Sigmund Freud's 1914 essay "Mourning and Melancholia" and the chapter "Violence, Mourning, Politics" of the book *Prearious Life: The Power of Mourning* by Judith Butler. Freud's 1919 essay "The Uncanny" and Freud's analysis of hysteria from "The Aetiology of Hysteria" have also been used briefly to support the study.

"Trauma and the Material Signifier" is a paper by Linda Belau that discusses the psychoanalytic explanation of trauma. Belau's study has supported this research with Jacques Lacan's understanding of trauma.

"Psychological theories of posttraumatic stress disorder" is a summarization of recent research on psychological processes to overcome PTSD, aiming to evaluate the theoretical model of this disorder.

"The Game of the Unconscious in Haruki Murakami's *Norwegian Wood*" by Supromit Maiti discusses the unconscious's effects on the characters' actions in *Norwegian Woods*, especially Naoko's suicide. This paper used the theories of multiple theorists like Freud and Lacan.

"Testimony and the Affirmation of Memory in Kazuo Ishiguro's *Never Let Me Go*" by Yugin Teo dives into the significance of memory in the novel. The clones were created in the world to die, helping humans. This paper showed that the clones' shared memory of growing up in their institution was the affirmation and testimony of their valid existence and collective identity. Authors Sarah Mahinthan, Isolde Nicolaysen, Alice Rita Olsen, and Inga Dóra Thórarinsdóttír discussed the existential questions in *Never Let Me Go* in their paper. They have acknowledged the absurdity of the characters' circumstances and

the characters' acceptance of their tragic destiny with Albert Camus' theory of "philosophical suicide."

"Mortality and Memory in Kazuo Ishiguro's *Never Let Me Go*" by Virginia Yeung explores the condition of humans being constantly aware of mortality or death, the "being-toward-death"-mode, according to Heidegger. This paper acknowledged that the novel mirrored the reality of humans.

Martin Šemelák discussed the suffering of the realization of death and existence in *Never Let Me Go*. The paper viewed the novel as Viktor Shklovsky's technique of defamiliarization and the world created in the novel as symbolic of human life.

Among the reviewed articles, the papers exploring existential questions and the documents containing Freudian psychoanalysis are the most similar to this research topic. However, this paper will take inspiration from all the reviewed articles.

ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

Mourning and Melancholia on *Norwegian Wood*

Memories Triggering Trauma

Toru's Inability to Forget

At the beginning of the narration, the story's present time, Toru Watanabe gets transported into the past as soon as the memories appear through a song. The memories of the past are no longer attacking him with trauma because a long time has passed. However, they are still hurting him. His memories of Naoko are neither forgotten nor vivid, which leaves him conflicted and perpetually broken. In Freud's concept, the negative ego of the mourner gets absorbed by the idea of the lost person (Freud, 1914, p. 249); the same phenomenon can be applied here to understand Toru's situation, which is absorbed by his promise to remember Naoko. His promise to remember her is also a reason for his disappointment in himself when he starts forgetting the details of Naoko's memories.

Naoko and Toru's Fixation with Kizuki

The center of both Toru and Naoko's trauma is Kizuki's death. Through Toru's flashback narrations, we can see that Toru is better than Naoko at accepting frustrating situations. Judith Butler explained a similar mourning process by emphasizing acceptance (Butler, 2004, p. 21). Though Toru had grief, he did not let himself be consumed by it.

It was strange for Naoko and Toru to turn 20; they wished to remain 17 like Kizuki, which was impossible. Having to inevitably leave the teenage years that connected her to Kizuki's memory, Naoko suffered from an intense meltdown on her birthday, when she gave herself in and slept with Toru to fulfill her desperate need to be comforted by someone. She wished it was Kizuki, but it was not. When Toru asked her why she and Kizuki did not consummate their relationship, the trauma of separation surged back. This became a breaking point for Naoko's fragile mental health, which indicates Post Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD). The memory of regret of being unable to be with Kizuki physically provoked her to collapse.

Midori's Acceptance of Trauma

Midori was a breath of fresh air in Toru's life. As Butler mentioned about the uncertainty of the transformation of loss and mourning (Butler, 2004, p. 21), Midori chose the positive path after she changed herself by successfully mourning. The memory of her mother's death did not contain bitterness anymore. The memories were of traumatic times, but they did not revoke her pain.

Midori also opened up about her idea of death. She wondered if she could faint in the smoke of an accidental fire and die peacefully. She did not imagine death with an obsession with ending her life due to melancholia. It was instead a confrontation of her wish for a peaceful and inevitable death. According to Butler's explanation of post-mourning positive transformation, that is, the acceptance of the loss (Butler, 2004, p. 21), and Freud's understanding of ideal mourning, that is, the ego's freedom from the grief of loss (Freud, 1914, p. 245), Midori's mourning is complete.

People from the Past called Naoko

Melancholia had been attached to Naoko even before Kizuki's death. Naoko's sister had committed suicide, and nobody had ever noticed any distress in her, just like Kizuki never showed any symptoms. Naoko vividly remembered the details of her sister's death and how traumatic it was. While this trauma had been suppressed, the trauma of Kizuki's death was added, further complicating her issues. Naoko's deteriorating condition can be observed in light of Freud's understanding of pathological Hysteria caused by a past trauma (Freud, 1914, p. 191). Her hallucinations were the aftereffects of her experience of her sister's death that got fueled even more by the grief of Kizuki's death. Her traumatic memories were so vivid that they created illusions for her as if calling her to the realm of death, making her deviate from life and reality.

Toru Juxtaposed in Mourning and Melancholia

While melancholia is the condition of the mourner's suffering, not knowing the cause, Toru still suffers from melancholia after Kizuki's death, while he knows what caused the suffering. Toru's encounter with the idea of death happened through Kizuki, which turned him somewhat apathetic toward his surroundings, and he knew why he felt that way. However, Naoko's loss put him into an unexpected turmoil of grief, denial, and helpless acceptance.

Toru was hopeful for a life with Naoko. He expected to comfort Naoko, embracing her with her issues. Making her feel better in her periods of nightmare was something that Toru was looking forward to. Naoko's death snatched his hopes away from him. Guilt was also added to his situation. Naoko's deteriorating condition made Toru feel guilty. Despite the responsibility, Toru tried to look forward and hope for the best. This is where he claimed he was different from Kizuki, who had not chosen to live with problems, but Toru himself was living. Melancholia is different from mourning, which causes intense and unconscious self-reproach. Following the same Freudian fashion, Toru went through such stages for the loss of Kizuki and Naoko; however, he consciously felt the experiences, acknowledging that he was not giving up despite wanting to.

Eventually, the news of Naoko's death left him in a state that was a mixture of pain and denial and the acceptance of pain and deprivation. He acknowledged the pain, knowing there was nothing to do about it. Toru's vagabond grief right after Naoko's death indicated that Naoko's loss and her memories were engulfing Toru. This was the initial level of mourning after a fresh loss where his ego could not withdraw the attachment from the lost loved one (Freud, 1914, p. 244). Toru started approaching melancholia as he contemplated if death was better than life. He started feeling a sense of comfort in his imagination of death, where he could reunite with Naoko and Kizuki and undo the pain, showing apparent symptoms of melancholia (Freud, 1914, p. 244).

Toru's self-awareness made him realize that he had been melancholic since Kizuki's death. He admitted that if Kizuki's death taught him about the proximity of death, Naoko's death revealed that no matter how unavoidable death was, losing someone he loved was always excruciating. His sufferings were not repressed but acknowledged by him. Toru's middle ground was accepting the inevitability of loss and death and recognizing the grief from loss and death, a strange place between successful mourning and the trap of melancholia. Butler's idea of the helpless state of melancholia fits Toru's situation (Butler, 2004, p. 21). He understood that he had nothing to do except dread himself in the uncontrollable state.

Stagnation and Confrontation of Trauma

Naoko's Unresolved Trauma Turning into Melancholia

Naoko succumbed to her suffering. She kept habitually wondering how ideal it would be if she could choose death. The lack of interest in continuing to live shows melancholia (Freud, 1914, p. 244).

The loss of Kizuki made her expect punishment from life, further making her believe that she would still be punished even if Kizuki had not died because disappointment was all she could expect from life. That is why Naoko seemed happy and emotional, reminiscing all the memories before committing suicide; she was releasing all the pain that could not be resolved and was preparing herself for the end. She also insisted that Toru remembered her no matter what. She was too tired and did not want to fight her insecurities and overcome them to live. The thought of being recognized by someone she loved was her only solace.

Naoko's vulnerability fed into her insecurities and growing conflicts of decisions and desires. She admitted that she felt safe with Toru, but she was also worried that he would not be happy with her because of her feebleness. Her fluctuating conception regarding the things around her eventually gets linked to Kizuki. When she remembered the night she spent with Toru, despite having admitted that she enjoyed it, she got agitated that Toru did not leave her alone. She wanted to be held close by someone to trust and love, especially Kizuki. However, he was not there. The trauma of separation from Kizuki is Naoko's inescapable "narcissistic obsession" (Freud, 1914, p. 249) with Kizuki's memory.

Confrontation and Sharing

The story briefly suggested a cure for the trauma that provided momentary peace for the characters. Naoko needed to seek help for her hysterical distress. In such cases, Freud recommended confrontation of the root of the problems (Freud, 1914, p. 195). Ami Hostel, Naoko's recovery institute, used conflict of trauma and openly talked about trauma as a powerful tool to help patients. Naoko showed improvements due to learning to actively discuss her suffering, which led her to empathize with Toru. She shared her and Kizuki's codependent intimacy that she could not escape after his death. Also, she admitted feeling guilty to have been able to physically open up to Toru, which she could not do with Kizuki when he was alive, the guilt that led to her breakdown. Naoko's understanding of the tremendous impact that Kizuki's death had on her and her sharing this realization with Toru was essential for them to confront the root of their sufferings.

Mourning and Melancholia in *Never Let Me Go*

The Loss that Has Already Been Mourned

Kathy, Ruth, Tommy, and all other clone humans of the institute Hailsham or outside the institute have suffered the loss of an ideal life. They have to live with the knowledge that their purpose is to go through a series of donations for ordinary humans till they die. This significant loss of the right to live life is demoralizing enough for them to be absorbed by the grief and slip into melancholia. According to Freud, the mourner starts suffering from melancholia when the sufferer's consciousness cannot shift its attachment from the loss to something else (Freud, 1914, p. 249). Melancholia is more plausible in this situation because the loss leaves no other option than waiting for death. However, *Never Let Me Go* makes survival and death more complex, simultaneously making it more straightforward by drawing parallels between the clones' fates and mortality.

The institute tried to justify its decision to hide the truth from the clone/students by claiming to have attempted to protect them from trauma and apathy towards life. Interestingly, though the students already got to know about their fate even before they were told, they still did not lose their interest in living.

The clones have constantly been aware of their loss and are in a continuous process of adjustment and transformation. Instead of completing the change and acquiring something new, their circumstances have compelled them to turn their adjustment period into their life. Thus, they have chosen to focus on what they must do during the loss instead of the loss itself. The clones who have become donors are looking forward to completing donating till they can die in peace. The carers ensure that the donors are taken care of properly until the carers' turn to contribute comes. This circumstance indicates a sign of completed mourning, where the sufferers have accepted their fate and are actively doing what they are assigned to do. Though they look forward to death, they have not abandoned their purpose in life.

The Institute's Contradiction

There has been a constant mention of the institute providing privileges to the clones with special care and kindness. Kathy admits that she and her friends have been lucky to belong to Hailsham. However, in the name of compassion, the institute planned to hide the facts from the students' truth to prevent trauma.

The possibility of students' exposure to trauma can be viewed through both Freud's and Lacan's theories. While discussing psychoanalysis, Jacques Lacan commented that realizing the traumatic event triggers trauma, which was unrecognizable (Lacan as qt in Belau, 2001). As for the clones of Hailsham, the traumas of organ donation and deprivation of everyday life were supposed to surface when Miss Lucy revealed these to them. Lacan's explanation can be compared with Freud's theory of the uncanny, which contradicts what occurs with Hailsham's children. Freud explained that the "uncanny" is some resurfaced repressed memory that the individual now experiences as something strange or scary (Freud, 1914, p. 1919). For the Hailsham students, the truth of their existence has always been familiar, and it remained normal without generating trauma even after being exposed to their consciousness.

The institute has been self-aware in blurring the line between kindness of secrecy and cruelty of betrayal. If the authorities had revealed the reality of the students, the students could have been traumatized. On the other hand, if the clones had been forced into their job of donation without prior knowledge of their state, they could have been more traumatized. Fortunately, the students already realized what their fate was. It was not explained how they knew, but they had been aware. Nevertheless, the students' self-sufficiency played a more prominent role in saving them from the trauma than the institute's attempted protection.

The institute also fluctuated from empathy to disgust for the students, claiming to have ensured their wellbeing and othering them for being clones. Miss Emily, the head of the institute, admitted to being repulsed by the students for not being typical humans. Despite being brought up with supposed special care, the students had to prove they had souls like humans with their artwork, which they mistook as a chance for deferral. The painting helped ease the students' disdain as a consolation that the clones were not strange creatures but humans. Miss Emily also pitied the students, knowing what had been awaiting them. At the same time, she could not do anything to try to change fate because the clones' sacrifice would help humankind.

Faint Expectations and Final Acceptance

Despite the students never rebelling against their fate, they still had desires and wondered how it would be if they could live like people outside the institutes. There have been two critical expectations of the students: their "possible" and the opportunity of deferral. The "possible" is considered to be the person each clone has originated from. Deferral is the rumor that the artwork collected from the students would determine which two clones can be compatible to be a couple and be granted a deferral. The story that Ruth's "possible" has been spotted makes her hope to see what kind of life her alternate version had been

living. When the rumor turns out to be false, she is disappointed. Considering her disappointment of the "possible" as an inevitable loss, her distressed reaction is also a part of her ego's mourning process and adjusting to the emptiness of disappointment (Freud, 1914, p. 244).

After Ruth's death, though Kathy is skeptical, Tommy remains hopeful about the deferral. They manage to talk to Miss Emily, only to learn that the rumor of deferral had never been confirmed and that the artworks were only to prove that the clones had souls like humans. Each piece of information is hurtful to Kathy and Tommy. The painful realization can also be considered the loss of a longtime hope they must mourn.

Soon after meeting Miss Emily, Tommy starts screaming the way he used to cry as a child during his anxiety attacks. Kathy observes that those outbursts as a child could be the effects of his repressed knowledge of their fate. Tommy's condition can also be viewed through Lacan's understanding of trauma. Tommy's outbursts resulted from the truth he knew but never acknowledged. Confrontation of that truth "commemorates" (Lacan as qt in Belau, 2001) the distress, leading him to the outburst of pain and the mourning process.

The novel ends with the consistent theme of acceptance. Both Kathy and Tommy have come to terms with the fact that fate must keep them apart despite them knowing now that they love each other. As Tommy's final donation is about to happen, Kathy and Tommy calmly say goodbye to each other. Kathy herself becomes a donor. Kathy and Tommy have freed themselves from the discomfort of grief and regret. They have accomplished Butler's idea of post-mourning transformation (Butler, 2004, p. 21) and Freud's idea of ego freedom (Freud, 1914, p. 245). Tommy and Kathy's final journey is equivalent to the completion of mourning.

CONCLUSION

Two different portrayals of mourning and melancholia are found in *Norwegian Wood* and *Never Let Me Go*. While in *Norwegian Wood*, the characters' melancholia is so profound that the idea of the end of life gives them relief, in *Never Let Me Go*, the characters' efficiency of adaptability and their completed mourning left no room for melancholia.

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